

"Optimization of Data Management for IOT through Quantum Block Chain Operations"

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ABSTRACT:

Over the past years, IoT has become a popular term in technology industries, which defines the network of different objects with any kind of sensors, software, and other technologies. Through IOT, things or object can exchange generated data over the internet. Cohesive Objects generates massive volume of data. Though we have many conventional methods of data management, they are not sufficient to accomplish all aspects of IOT. A new technology technique called Quantum Block Chain has emerged in the last few days. Blockchain technology uses quantum information theory and quantum computation to create a distributed database that is decentralized, encrypted. This paper will present utility of blockchain system with IOT.

Keywords: IOT, Block Chain, Quantum blockchain, Data management, Operation System.

INTRODUCTION:

Internet Of Things(IOT):

IoT stands for Internet of Things and is regarded as one of the new technologies that is used to express a modern network of wireless telecommunications. IoT can be defined as a brainy and interoperable node within a global wireless infrastructure that allows for connectivity anywhere, at any time. IOT is being envisioned as a place where there are numerous interconnected objects, containing sensors, AI, and internet access. The interconnected objects are termed as "Things", and these "Things" are continually communicated with each other over the internet and passing data/information via sensors [1]. The main goal of IOT is expand the utility of internet through integrate the physical world and virtual world to exchange information [2]. Briefly IOT has a capability to transfer the data over the network without the interaction of human and/or machine [3].

IOT and Data Management:

Various smart objects are interconnected to form IOT networking architecture. As part of the IoT initiative, economic and energy-efficient hardware is being developed for these objects, as well as connectivity technologies to connect objects. Though, these connected objects produce massive amount of data and need mature solutions to manage and utilize data. Produced data are real time and stored in permanent repository. From dynamic and mobile objects to concentration storage points, IoT data will reside statically in databases based on a fixed or flexible schema [1]. State-of-the-art knowledge-based information can be mine from the stored data and can make value added avantgarde application. Application may tend to irreplaceable source of information to analyzing for strategic prospects. Accessibility of data are completely depending on the privacy framework of network in which IOTs are interconnected.

In many IOT applications machines and human user intermingles by cyber physics system that's why owed to the miscellany and heterogeneousness data generated for these data traditional database management systems is not appropriate [4].

Figure 1 IOT Data Collection frame work[5]

METHODOLOGY:

This work is based of literature survey. First identifying delinquent, problems in existing data management system for IOT generated data. Then will points the features of blockchain operation system with the help of present work has been done. this work will present how features of blockchain can be a solution of data management.

BACKGROUND:

YimingJiang and others mentioned in “A Cross-Chain Solution to Integrating Multiple Blockchains for IoT Data Management” (2019), that now a days millions of devices are linked in IoT pose more substantial challenges to data management. Maximum existing solutions of problems in data management of IOT specify centralized systems, which carries about the privacy and security issues[6].

Tongrang Fan, Yanzhao Chen and others defined in “A scheme of data management in the Internet of Things”(2010), that the heterogeneity of devices and technologies carries challenges in IOT, particularly in the management of assorted data. They mentioned SOA approach as an effective solution. In SOA, the structure of the Internet of Things is analysed, and a web-based services were designed for data management framework of the Internet of Things [7].

Mengyao Zhang and others stated that the blockchain and information technology having powerful connectivity for data management. A lightweight security system can be apply on E-comm data for security to achieve better result.[8].

HaoWang and others proposed a new framework based on the blockchain technology for the data privacy in management financial sector. Which have three components likewise a data privacy classification method according to the characteristics of financial data;a new collaborative-filtering-based model and a data disclosure confirmation scheme for customer strategies [9].

Sultan and others explained, because of deployment in smart homes and city developments round the world IoT has expanded its acceptance. IoT network devices, on the other hand, have limited

computational power, storage space, and network bandwidth. As a result, they are more vulnerable to assaults than other end-point devices like mobile phones, tablets, or computers. This study focuses on major IoT security challenges and maps IoT security issues in opposition to existing solutions available in the literature. Furthermore, concerns that have not been resolved as a result of blockchain deployment are mentioned[25].

Alam, Tanweerdiscuss in their work is , Blockchain's role in the Internet of Things is to provide a method for securely processing data records across IoT nodes. Blockchain is a safe and open technology that may be utilised by anyone. This type of technology is required for IoT to facilitate safe communication across IoT nodes in a heterogeneous environment. Anyone who is authenticated to communicate within the IoT can track and investigate Blockchain transactions. In the IoT, Blockchain could help to increase communication security. In this study, I looked into this approach, its benefits and drawbacks.

Faiza Loukil and others said Individuals' quality of life is projected to increase as a result of the Internet of Things (IoT). Due to the poor competence of these linked devices, providing security and privacy in the IoT context is a difficult task. The management of IoT devices is often based on a centralised entity that verifies communication and connection privileges. As a result, this central entity might be thought of as a single point of failure [29].

CHALLENGES IN IOT DATA MANAGEMENT:

The idea behind Internet of Things is to generate consistent data from small devices. Generated data will then support the decision makers, data scientist and researchers to take a decision on the enormous amount of data [10]. The other side of coin is, devices which are integrated will producing data at a very high rate, which would need a huge amount of storage space and robust, durable data management system. Other than the data there are multiple other challenges posed by these devices. As in all over world IOT technology rapidly grow also generate to issues and challenges that need to There are many IoT services are being used such as smart home, smart city, smart car healthcare, industrial automation and city traffic management etc. in real world. Whereas on the other side developers facing lots of challenges, which are identified in IoT services. According to study challenges mainly involve data security, data storage, data integrity, data processing, data heterogeneity, knowledge management and data analysis tools.

Figure 2: Challenges in IOT Data management

Some challenges are in detail

Data storage:

IOT researchers and data scientists may increasingly be concerned about data storage and management. Because IOT involves physical objects such as sensors or devices that communicate over the Internet, the question of storage of data produced by many objects will be raised by the massive human population. These interconnected IoT devices accumulate data from the environment by using sensors, audio devices, cameras, radio frequency identifier, light frequency identifier etc [7]. In IoT applications, we can improve this challenge by collecting, managing, and storing data generated during IoT processes. Furthermore, we need tools for analysing the data in order to improve industrial decisions and increase performance and output across different fields [15].

Security and Privacy:

Adding IoT devices and utilizing this technology in daily work activities can generate a great deal of personal data since this technology is embedded in the work environment. With respect to many aspects of IoT Systems, security and privacy issues are imperatives for developing confidence [16]. As IOTs are working on network so privacy mechanisms must be present in data retrieval and knowledge mining process to prevent by unauthorised access.

Scalability, Availability and Reliability

An infrastructure can be scalable if it is proficient to add more computer, servers, new services, equipment and devices in a network in order to manage work load without affecting the performance [18]. In IoT, the main challenge is the need to support devices of different memory, processing, and storage capacities. The availability must also be considered. In the IoT layered framework, both scalability and availability should be considered.

Integrity:

In other words, data integrity is the accuracy, consistency, and completeness of data. In terms of regulatory compliance, such as GDPR compliance, and data security, data integrity refers to the safety of data. One of the most important issues in any data-centric environment is data integrity [18]. Devices that collect sensor data must ensure that only the data necessary for required operations is collected and shared. Data must not be stored or shared indefinitely. In order to collect and exchange data, some standard rules and procedures should be used with a reasonable level of integrity.

Knowledge Discovery

IoT, the state of almost anything else can be followed, configured and stored on different computer systems using user devices or remotely from server endpoints. Status determination can be easily identified by data mining techniques that follow a different level up to the representation of information [18]. Data cleaning, retrieval, model recognition, and summary techniques were considered challenging tasks due to the nature of IoT settings. This also required a new research approach to come up with improved service delivery in the IoT environment.

BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain basically a database of transactional record, but it is differed from conventional database as in it record of transaction is scattered. That's why initially it is associated with bitcoin so that records of transaction can be monitored, validate by a community not by a single authority.

The main keyword which may attract researchers of integration of Blockchain and IOT is blockchain permits anyone who is in network to access others data. When one transaction is completed, the new transaction is linked with old one. in this way chain is establishing, so it is calling Blockchain[20].

A journal of rapidly growing list of records is in blockchain which framing the blocks. The blocks are linked and secured by cryptography algorithms. Every block is cryptographical information about previous block, transactional details, content of block and time stamp. As blockchain is distributed so all blocks in the grid have incomparable identifiers which are attached to the blocks as headers. The block headers store the above-mentioned information[12]. The records in those blockchains are kept in such a way that every update, whether in the form of transactions or any other digital event, is recorded and validated using certain consensus mechanisms.

Blockchain network concept explain working of blockchain in better way. Blockchain network consist is a set of nodes usually called clients that activate on the same blockchain by the holding copy each one. A node act as an entry point for several different blockchain users into the network.

A pair of private/public keys is used by users to communicate with the blockchain. They sign their own transactions with their private key, and their public key allows them to be addressed on the network. The use of asymmetric cryptography in the network provides authentication, integrity, and non-repudiation. A user's node broadcasts every signed transaction to its one-hop peers[21].

Before transmitting this incoming transaction further, the adjacent peers verify that it is genuine; invalid transactions are discarded. This transaction eventually spreads over the entire network.

The network arranges and packages the transactions that have been collected and validated by the process above during an agreed-upon time interval into a timestamped candidate block. This is referred to as mining. This block is broadcast back to the network by the mining node. The nodes check that the proposed block contains legitimate transactions and refers to the correct preceding block on their chain through hash. If this is the case, they add the block to their chain and update their world view with the transactions it includes. The proposed block is discarded if this is not the case. A round comes to an end when this happens.

QUANTUM BLOCKCHAIN

Quantum blockchain is a new technology related to the IoT and it can be seen as a decentralized or distributed data store, point to point transmission, encryption algorithms, and consensus mechanism. The bitcoin technology framework is itself follows decentralized server in which each node contains a copy of blockchain database and it has advantage that the information stored in this cannot be altered or changed illegally, so it has a wide range of application such as smart cities, information security, industry application and digital currency like bitcoin [8].

The scalability, efficiency, and long-term viability of blockchain technology are all major concerns. If blockchain is to become a technology that can be utilised responsibly, these issues must be addressed. By the time blockchain is extensively adopted for mission-critical work at banking and other organisations, useful quantum computers may have been constructed[22]. Quantum computing will not only pose issues for blockchain, but it can also be used to improve the implementation of some aspects of the technology.

While Blockchain provides a platform for conducting a secure and transparent transaction, quantum computing is the next generation of computing devices that will make all tasks simple and quick. Subatomic particles are used in quantum computing. At any given time, these particles will exist in more than one state. Because of this one-of-a-kind feature, the computing process is significantly

faster than what we have now. Quantum computing, in addition to being faster, also consumes less energy than existing computer equipment.

A blockchain is a form of traditional database that stores historical data, such as financial (or other) transactions. Its one-of-a-kind design makes it extremely impossible to tamper with, and it doesn't require a centralised organisation to keep track of its accuracy. Scalable quantum computers could successfully breach the cryptographic algorithms used to safeguard (classical) blockchains, as well as the digital security of the current world, according to a recent study [24].

Quantum Blockchain is involvement of Quantum computing and Quantum cryptography in blockchain technology. Quantum cryptography is a fascinating area that employs quantum mechanics to create a cryptosystem that is thought to be the most secure in the world[8]. It cannot be breached by anyone without the sender or receiver of the message being notified. Because it is impossible to gauge the quantum state of any system without upsetting it, quantum cryptography relies on photons and their underlying quantum features to create an indestructible cryptosystem[23].

HOW QUANTUM BLOCKCHAIN SOLVES THE DATA MANAGEMENT PROBLEM:

Internet of things is one of the fastest emerging areas of research and it is also a technique which is very closely related to the human day to day life like smart doors, smart cities etc. One of the problems of IoT is the management of large amount of data, which are being processed and stored in central repository every second. Managing the large amount of data and securing the data is one of the important and tedious tasks of IoT therefore quantum Block-chain technology has emerged as a one of the possible solutions to the problems. There are number of benefits of using blockchain in IoT application [8]. In this section we will discuss about the problem and the solution using quantum block-chain technique.

- **Data Security:** Data security is one of the important aspects of today era and the way large amount of data is being generated by IoT applications every second, it is very important to care about the security of these generated data [12]. Blockchain technology has been emerged as a one of the possible solution for security of data as in this technique the IoT application is designed based on decentralized server so it reduces the threat to the data security by saving the data at different- different location rather than saving all data at one single repository.

Blockchain can offer strong security as Blockchain 's entries is the only can be appended . The information in the Blockchain directory cannot be changed or modified, that is, all entries are permanent entries. In addition, all inputs are included with the digital signatories of the issuers[20]. Therefore, Blockchain technology provides better security for user data and transaction data.

- **Reduces the time to process the data:** The time taken to process any data is one of the important matrices for any IoT application and the performance of the entire application depends on this. The lesser the time taken for processing improves the system performance. Introducing the blockchain techniques has motivated the used of edge computing in the IoT applications, which leads to the superior system performance. In edge computing techniques the data is processed in between the IoT smart devices and central repository using edge device and it can save lots of time of data processing.
- **Ease the data exchange:** Exchange of data is one of the important aspects of every IoT devices. Earlier the involvement of IoT gateways and other intermediate devices has made

the process of data exchange very tedious, which may lead to slow down of the entire IoT application but introducing the blockchain eliminates the gateway and other intermediate devices which leads to involvement of edge devices for IoT applications. IoT data exchange services are surfacing to connect varied and dispersed IoT data sources, allowing data owners to exchange their IoT data more easily. Traditional IoT data exchange systems enlist the help of a centralized third-party to settle trades between data consumers and producers. Single point of failure, additional settlement fees, and lack of openness of settlement facts, to mention a few drawbacks of this settlement mechanism[25]. Blockchain is a cutting-edge technology capable of controlling a decentralized network, presenting a significant prospect for decentralized fair settlement.

- **Tracing of device communication:** Communication between two or more IoT devices is back born of any IoT application and introducing the blockchain also helps to track the communication between two IoT devices by applying various protocols in such a way that the objective of application can be met. Blockchain technology can track billions of connected devices and facilitate transaction processing and coordination. It is a missing link that tackles many of the IoT industry's security and privacy challenges, and it saves IoT companies and manufacturers a lot of money[22]. It has the potential to offer a more resilient operating environment for appliances, as well as reducing costs for both manufacturers and customers.

The decentralized fabric of blockchain also allows smart contracts and smart contract agents to be deployed on the edge of an IoT network, speeding up transactions at the fabric's edges. IoT devices are likely to slow down — but blockchain networks can handle this without affecting transaction speeds or data flow [26]. Blockchain and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies are continually changing, addressing old issues and introducing new ones. As a result of this convergence, developers must consider security, privacy, and data security, along with compatibility between IoT devices and blockchain.

- **Autonomous function of smart devices:** The involvement of blockchain allows smart devices to function autonomously as it doesn't need the central repository. The autonomous functioning can be seen as a one of the important aspect for any smart devices. Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that works in tandem with the Internet of Things to enable machine-to-machine interactions. It employs a set of transactions that are stored in a database, double-checked by numerous sources, and recorded in a shared ledger that spans all nodes[20]. The nuptial of IoT and blockchain offers a number of potential benefits, including the ability for a smart device to operate independently of a centralized authority. It can also monitor how gadgets interact with one another.

While blockchain's decentralized nature is an architectural benefit, it can be a difficulty for IoT. Client-server or hub-and-spoke architecture, which is a centralized authority, is used by IoT platforms. Building a decentralized IoT platform will make it easier to integrate with a blockchain network.

- **Prevent system from failure:** The IoT application is fully rely on the communication made by the various IoT devices in such a way that full fills the objective of IoT applications but slow done or failure of one devices/server can lead to the shutdown of all application but the use of blockchain technique can overcome this issue using the high level security by authorizing and authenticating the encrypted device generated data using the de-centralized and distributed ledger.

This idea is built on a 'Peer to Peer dispersed' network that is enabled by IoT and block chain. The decentralized nature of peer-to-peer (P2P) networks improves robustness by eliminating the single point of failure that might occur in a client-server system. The total capacity of the system grows as additional nodes are added and demand on the system grows, and the risk of failure lowers. The network as a whole is not compromised if one peer fails to function properly. Clients share only their needs with the system in a normal client-server design, but not their resources.

- **Reduces the maintenance cost:** The use of blockchain can reduce the maintenance cost by introducing the concept of distributed ledger in IoT application and it also minimize the risk associated with the application. The ability to work as a team independently People can unite together and act as a group using blockchain technology. They can be self-sufficient as a group, lowering expenses by removing middlemen from the transaction process and completing transactions as a group.
- **Data Privacy:** Privacy of data is one of the important aspects of blockchain technique. It ensures that no data can be altered [13] in the system and this is just because of the immutable, trustworthy and storage feature of the blockchain's technology. Moreover the blockchain allows a user to see the transaction across the network so that computer and data rights are retained. Through social media, blockchain protects private information. One can secure, authenticate, and interact with blockchain, and this field is expected to increase in the future.

The administration of IoT devices is based on a centralized body that verifies communication and connection permissions. As a result, this central entity might be thought of as a single point of failure. However, in untrustworthy IoT contexts, it is difficult to delegate the appropriate validation to IoT devices themselves when using dispersed techniques. Fortunately, the blockchain may be able to enable decentralization in order to solve the trust problem while still maintaining anonymity[29,28]. The IoT devices are managed by numerous smart contracts that validate connection privileges based on the data owners' privacy permission settings and the stored record array of identified IoT device misbehavior. Smart contracts, in fact, can detect devices that are vulnerable, have been hacked, or represent a threat to the IoT network right away. As a result, the privacy of the data owner is protected by imposing control over one's own devices. Validation may be done on the blockchain.

- **Reduces the operational cost:** The use of blockchain eliminates any third party application or middleman for ensuring the safety and security of the system therefore the operational or business cost is reduced [14]. Blockchain solutions provide a number of critical advantages, including the capacity to boost trust, transparency, and predictability of results by allowing shipments to be tracked at any moment. Blockchain functions as an immutable ledger in a decentralized environment, allowing any changes in ownership and possession of items, as well as their movements from producer to retailer, to be recorded promptly for improved accuracy [10]. Blockchain technology has the potential to solve some of these problems. The adoption of smart contracts, for example, which are automatically activated when a specified activity occurs, could help to reduce the role of intermediaries. The usage of blockchain technology can aid inventory management, decrease costly data inaccuracies and delays, and speed up dispute settlement [28].

Figure 3: advantage of using Blockchain

Conclusion:

This article examines the current issues and risks with IoT systems, focusing on the issues of authenticity, integrity, and responsiveness. This integration intends to simplify data management in IoT applications while also ensuring transparency, security, and traceability of data flows between untrustworthy counterparties. IoT has become a key aspect of modern computing, especially for large-scale computing infrastructures, because to the rapid technical progress of computing devices.

The Internet of Things has numerous applications in various fields. The current challenges and concerns with IoT systems are examined in this article, with a focus on the topics of authenticity, integrity, and responsiveness. This integration aims to simplify data management in IoT applications while also ensuring data flows between untrustworthy counterparties are transparent, secure, and traceable. Because of the continuous technological advancement of computing devices, the Internet of Things has become a vital feature of modern computing, particularly for large-scale computing infrastructures. The Internet of Things has a wide range of uses in a variety of fields.

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